

A TAXONOMY OF INCIDENT MANAGEMENT IN PROPRIETARY SOFTWARE ECOSYSTEMS

This briefing reports scientific evidence on the challenges of developing a taxonomy of incident management to support organizations' management teams in the proprietary software ecosystem (PSECO) context.

FINDINGS

- **Organizations are experiencing rapid and frequent changes to their business models.** Implement agile incident management practices to adapt to rapid business model changes and sustain the evolving common technological platform in PSECO.
- **Delivery speed.** An incident management approach is crucial for PSECO to mitigate disruptions and ensure timely delivery amid rapid technology updates and customer expectations.
- **Organizational culture.** Resistance to transitioning from traditional to agile ITSM methods hampers pace, increases costs, and reduces operational efficiency, hindering adaptation to necessary business changes.
- **Outdated ITSM practices.** Bureaucratic ITSM practices hinder modern business needs. Thus, embracing comprehensive service delivery approaches is essential for adapting to rapid business model shifts and faster delivery demands.
- **Automated and integrated monitoring tools.** Automation in ITSM enhances incident prediction, addressing the complexities in environments such as PSECO by monitoring, detection, and resolution capabilities within the technological platform.
- **Integration of quality and incident management.** Use of software quality practices within incident management for PSECO, mitigating incidents by adopting robust development methods such as rigorous testing, code reviews, and performance stress.

- **Blameless post-mortem incidents.** Post-critical incident meetings analyze incident causes, aiming to prevent future occurrences. Emphasis lies on learning rather than attributing blame to individuals or teams.

TAXONOMY

Goals

- Reduce incident response time;
- Reduce resolution time;
- Reduce the number of incidents in the backlog.

Strategies

- Establish incident response plans;
- Adopt real-time incident monitoring;
- Automate incident management processes;
- Coordinate cross-functional collaboration;
- Maintain incident knowledge base;
- Perform post-incident reviews;
- Manage incidents caused by changes;
- Collect end-user feedback.

Factors

- Organizational culture;
- Qualified teams;
- Proactive monitoring;
- Communication with stakeholders;
- IT providers and third-parties;
- End-user feedback.

Benefits

- Improve customer satisfaction;
- Increase operational efficiency;
- Save costs;
- Improve the organization's reputation;
- Increase resilience.

Barriers

- Lack of clear goal setting by IT board;
- Limited budget;
- Lack of qualified professionals;
- Organizational culture resistant to change management;
- Lack of adequate supporting tools.

Who is this briefing for?

Software engineering practitioners who want to make decisions about incident management to support organizations' management teams in the proprietary software ecosystem (PSECO) context based on scientific evidence.

Where the findings come from?

All findings of this briefing were extracted from the scientific studies about incident management identified on a rapid review carried out by <AUTHOR 1> et al.<<omitted due to blind review>>

What is included in this briefing?

The framework consists of five core categories: goals, practices, success factors, benefits, and barriers. These categories emerged from the analysis of scientific studies.

What is not included in this briefing?

Findings that are not based on scientific studies.

To access other evidence briefings on software engineering:

<https://eseg.cin.ufpe.br/links-importantes/evidence-briefings>